

Article

Behavioral Engagement in VR-Based Sign Language Learning: Visual Attention as a Predictor of Performance and Temporal Dynamics

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Abstract

Understanding how learners engage with immersive sign language training environments is essential for advancing virtual reality-based education and inclusion. This study analyzes behavioral engagement in SONAR, a virtual reality application designed for sign language training and validation. We focus on three automatically derived engagement indicators (Visual Attention (VA), Video Replay Frequency (VRF), and Post-Playback Viewing Time (PPVT)) and examine their relationship with learning performance in a sample of 117 university students. Participants completed a self-paced Training phase with 12 sign language instructional videos, followed by a Validation quiz assessing retention. We employed Pearson correlation analysis to examine the relationships between engagement indicators and quiz performance, followed by binomial Generalized Linear Model (GLM) regression to assess their joint predictive contributions. Additionally, we conducted temporal analysis by aggregating moment-to-moment VA traces across all learners to characterize engagement dynamics during the learning session. Results show that VA exhibits a strong positive correlation with quiz performance ($r = 0.76$), followed by PPVT ($r = 0.66$), whereas VRF shows no meaningful association. A binomial GLM confirms that VA and PPVT are significant predictors of learning success, jointly explaining a substantial proportion of performance variance ($pseudo - R^2 = 0.83$). Going beyond outcome-oriented analysis, we characterize temporal engagement patterns by aggregating moment-to-moment VA traces across all learners. The temporal profile reveals distinct attention peaks aligned with informationally dense segments of both training and validation videos, as well as phase-specific engagement dynamics, including initial acclimatization, oscillatory attention cycles during learning, and pronounced attentional peaks during assessment. Together, these findings highlight the central role of sustained and strategically allocated visual attention in VR-based sign language learning and demonstrate the value of behavioral trace data for understanding and predicting learner engagement in immersive environments.

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1. Introduction

Virtual reality (VR) has demonstrated significant potential for enhancing learning outcomes across diverse educational domains [1]. The immersive nature of VR enables embodied, multimodal learning experiences particularly suited for skill-based domains such as sign language instruction [2], where learners must simultaneously encode hand-shape, orientation, movement, location, and facial expressions. Recent systematic reviews confirm that VR-based sign language learning systems produce measurable improvements in learning outcomes and engagement compared to conventional instruction [3].

Despite these promising developments, a critical gap persists in the literature: while studies document the general effectiveness of VR sign language systems, they have not systematically examined how objective behavioral engagement indicators extracted from learner interactions relate to user engagement. Contemporary VR learning research emphasizes behavioral metrics derived from built-in tracking: head and hand movements, movement entropy, and exploration patterns. These metrics can be used as synchronous indicators of engagement and intrinsic motivation, providing real-time insight into cognitive states [4]. Indeed, these behavioral indicators are scalable, continuously available from the learning platform, and can support real-time adaptive feedback without additional instrumentation.

The present study addresses this gap by proposing the following research questions: (i) Which specific behavioral indicators, automatically captured during VR interaction, predict learning success in sign language training? and (ii) Do these indicators evolve dynamically throughout the learning process? Addressing these questions is essential for developing adaptive VR learning systems that can provide real-time support based on learner engagement patterns. Specifically, we examined how three indicators of behavioral engagement, namely Visual Attention (VA), Post-Playback Viewing Time (PPVT), and Video Replay Frequency (VRF), correlate with learning performance, and we employed a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) regression to evaluate their combined predictive power. Finally, we analyzed how VA changes over the course of the interaction with the VR sign language application.

Our framework is grounded in established learning science theories: eye-tracking research establishing gaze duration as a proxy for cognitive engagement [5,6], cognitive load theory identifying fixation patterns as indicators of information processing [7], and self-regulated learning theory showing that voluntary content revisits reflect metacognitive strategies [8,9]. Specifically, this study examines learner engagement in SONAR (the interested reader can find the application at the following link: <https://sidequestvr.com/app/37864/> (accessed on 1 March 2026)), a VR application developed within the ISENSE project for sign language training. This application places users in the role of a hearing student interacting with a deaf avatar on a simulated university campus during the first day of class. The participants, 117 university students, completed a self-paced Training phase that allowed video replays, followed by a Validation quiz aimed at assessing retention. We then evaluate whether the engagement indicators are associated with learning success by relating them to quiz performance through correlational analyses and regression-based modeling. In addition, we move beyond aggregate measures by examining how visual attention changes over time throughout the interaction, highlighting temporal engagement patterns across the learning and assessment phases.

Our principal findings are threefold: (i) VA and PPVT are strong, statistically significant predictors of learning performance, with VA emerging as the dominant indicator; (ii) VRF shows negligible correlation with performance, suggesting that engagement quality supersedes repetition quantity; (iii) temporal analysis reveals structured engagement patterns with characteristic peaks during training and assessment phases, confirming the task-driven nature of the observed attention patterns. These findings extend recent work

on learning analytics into sign language VR contexts [10]. Practically, these metrics can be automatically computed to enable real-time attention-aware learning analytics, supporting adaptive instructional interventions such as refocusing prompts or targeted content review.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews literature on VR for education, VR-based sign language instruction, and engagement measurement in immersive environments. Section 3 describes the SONAR VR application. Section 4 formally introduces the engagement framework and research questions. Section 5 presents the study design and data collection procedures. Section 6 reports quantitative analyses addressing the research questions. Section 7 interprets findings in the context of prior work and discusses limitations. Section 8 summarizes contributions and implications for adaptive VR learning systems.

2. Related Work

This section positions our work in relation to existing research on VR-based education, inclusion, and engagement measurement, with a specific focus on sign language learning. Specifically, in Section 2.1, we review research on VR for education, highlighting evidence on learning gains, motivational benefits, and design challenges. Section 2.2 examines VR and inclusion, summarizing studies on accessibility, inclusive design, and applications for deaf and hard-of-hearing (DHH) learners and sign language education. Finally, Section 2.3 discusses engagement in VR, covering multidimensional models of engagement, behavioral and gaze-based indicators, and the limited existing work on engagement metrics in VR sign language learning.

2.1. Education and VR

Research consistently demonstrates VR's positive impact on learning outcomes, with robust effects in healthcare [1] and significant advantages over less immersive methods in scientific domains like biology and physics [11]. This effectiveness is largely attributed to VR's ability to facilitate embodied, constructivist learning experiences where users actively construct knowledge through direct interaction [4].

In language learning, VR instruction yields significant benefits for speaking, listening, and vocabulary acquisition [12,13]. Educational outcomes are further enhanced by optimizing learner–environment interactivity [14] and integrating gamification, which substantially boosts motivation and engagement compared to non-gamified approaches [15].

Despite these benefits, adoption is limited by barriers such as hardware costs, content scarcity, integration challenges, and potential cybersickness [16]. Consequently, hybrid approaches combining VR with conventional instruction often yield superior outcomes, suggesting VR is most effective as a complementary tool within broader instructional designs rather than as a standalone replacement [17].

2.2. VR and Inclusion

VR advances inclusive education for students with disabilities, with systematic reviews confirming enhanced social inclusion and skill development [18,19]. Accessibility features such as text-to-speech, customizable avatars, and high-contrast visuals significantly improve motivation and learning outcomes [20], particularly for intellectual disabilities where immersive VR outperforms non-immersive methods [21]. However, barriers persist, requiring collaborative user-centered design processes [22,23].

For DHH individuals and sign language learners, VR offers unique benefits through sign language support and real-time captioning [24], guided by XR design principles emphasizing communication clarity [25]. Key innovations include AI gesture recognition, gamification, and interactive environments [3], with 3D VR demonstrating superior en-

gement and efficiency over 2D systems [2,26]. Recent technical solutions, such as inverse kinematics tracking [27], enhanced hand reconstruction [28], and ISENSE sign detection frameworks [29], further expand VR's potential for accessible sign language education.

2.3. Engagement in VR

Engagement in educational settings is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct encompassing behavioral, emotional, and cognitive dimensions [30,31]. In VR learning environments, behavioral engagement reflects observable participation and interaction with the digital environment, cognitive engagement relates to mental effort and comprehension, and emotional engagement captures motivational responses [32]. VR environments are effective at eliciting engagement through immersion, interactivity, and embodied learning experiences. A systematic review of VR impact on student engagement found that VR positively influences cognitive engagement by facilitating understanding of complex and abstract knowledge through immersive learning experiences, behavioral engagement through increased active participation and motivation, and affective engagement through emotional involvement and empathy development [32].

2.3.1. Measuring Engagement in VR

A critical challenge in VR learning research is the operationalization and measurement of engagement. Recent work emphasizes the importance of objective, automatically-derived behavioral indicators that can be extracted from VR interaction logs without additional hardware or manual analysis [33,34]. These behavioral traces offer distinct advantages over physiological measures alone, as they directly reflect learners' observable choices and the temporal allocation of effort during the learning task. Learning analytics provides a strong framework for analyzing students' learning processes and engagement via trace data collected from learning environments [35].

Visual Attention and Gaze-Based Indicators

Eye-tracking and head-tracking provide direct measures of behavioral engagement, utilizing metrics such as fixation duration and saccade frequency to assess cognitive attention allocation [5,6,36]. Research distinguishes between ambient and focal attention modes, noting that fixation duration correlates with task difficulty and cognitive load [7,37]. In immersive environments, these gaze patterns serve as temporal indicators of engagement, where metrics like the ambient/focal coefficient track how learners process visual stimuli [5]. For skill-based tasks like sign language, sustained visual focus on the model is critical for encoding motor details, making gaze orientation a valid proxy for task-relevant engagement [38].

Behavioral Traces from Video Interaction Logs

Automated interaction logs capture self-regulated learning strategies, where behaviors like pausing for reflection or selective re-watching reflect active engagement [8,39]. These strategic adjustments allow learners to align content pacing with their processing capacity [9], distinguishing high-performing active learners from passive viewers [40]. Machine learning analyses of such clickstream data have effectively modeled engagement states and predicted learning outcomes [41], representing distinct facets of engagement such as effort and content interest [35].

Multimodal Measurement Approaches

While physiological measures can assess emotional states, behavioral metrics are more scalable and have been shown to correlate more strongly with learning outcomes [42]. Reviews confirm the value of combining gaze metrics with behavioral data to assess

cognitive states [43]. Consequently, this study concentrates on these objective, automatically derivable indicators to examine their relationship with performance in a motor-intensive sign language task.

2.3.2. Motor Learning and Engagement in VR

Research on motor learning in immersive VR demonstrates its capacity to support the acquisition of complex movements under controlled conditions [44]. Notably, studies report that VR practice can yield performance improvements comparable to real-world training, establishing a functional link between visual attention patterns (e.g., quiet-eye) and motor skill acquisition [45].

Embodied learning perspectives further emphasize the sensorimotor coupling between perception, action, and attention, where distinct interaction techniques directly influence performance [38]. Recent work argues that learners refine internal motor representations through an integrated loop of observation and enactment [46,47]. Consequently, sign language training in VR works as observational motor learning, where behavioral indicators, such as visual orientation toward the signer, serve as operational proxies for the attentional resources allocated to encoding complex manual and facial movements.

2.3.3. Engagement in VR-Based Sign Language Education

As discussed in Section 2.1, VR systems for sign language education have demonstrated positive impacts on learning outcomes compared to traditional instructional materials [26], indeed gamified 3D VR environments produce higher engagement and retention than 2D alternatives [2]. A recent systematic review on VR in sign language education identifies gesture recognition and real-time feedback as key mechanisms through which VR sustains learner engagement [3].

However, research directly linking objective behavioral engagement indicators extracted from VR logs to measurable learning outcomes in sign language education remains limited. Existing studies on VR for sign language education have primarily focused on general effectiveness assessments and usability evaluations [2,3,26]. To the best of our knowledge, no prior study has examined how automatically-derived behavioral engagement indicators from VR interaction correlate with learning performance in sign language training applications. This represents a significant gap in the literature. Indeed, while general research on VR learning demonstrates that behavioral traces can predict engagement and performance [33,34,42], the specific application of such approaches to sign language learning remains unexplored. Moreover, the broader question of how learners' engagement unfolds and changes over time during sign language VR interaction, has not been addressed in any prior work.

The present study directly addresses both of these gaps: (1) by examining the relationship between automatically-captured behavioral engagement indicators and learning outcomes in a VR sign language context, and (2) by analyzing how learners' engagement patterns evolve and change during interaction, revealing temporal dynamics of user engagement with the sign language VR application. This dual focus connects outcome-oriented analysis (how engagement relates to performance) with process-oriented analysis (how engagement changes over time), providing insights into both the effectiveness of behavioral metrics for predicting sign language learning and the dynamics of user engagement in immersive educational environments.

3. App Description

The SONAR application is a VR platform developed within and supported by the ISENSE project (<https://www.isenseproject.eu/> (accessed on 1 March 2026)), an Erasmus+

funded initiative focused on inclusive higher education for deaf and hard-of-hearing students. The application was designed and implemented by some members of the current authorial team as part of this project. The interested reader can find the application at the following link: <https://sidequestvr.com/app/37864/> (accessed on 1 March 2026). It places users in the role of a hearing student interacting with a deaf avatar on a simulated university campus during the first day of class. The experience is structured into two distinct phases: Training and Validation. Users can interact with the virtual environment using either controllers or hand gestures.

3.1. Overview

The participant finds themselves on their first day of class at university, inside a tiered lecture hall. At the beginning of the experience, they are able to navigate through the classroom and observe the different virtual elements present in the environment, such as the blackboard, classmates interacting with each other, textbooks, and other objects. In one of the seats, Essie, a deaf classmate, can be found, with whom the participant can interact to communicate using sign language.

Upon approaching Essie, the application presents the user with two options: Training and Validation. Once one of these options is selected, whose differences will be explained later, a conversation in sign language is initiated. During this interaction, the participant is shown how to sign several basic phrases that can be used to introduce oneself and establish an initial contact with a classmate. The conversation consists of 12 interactions, each composed of one user contribution followed by a response from the deaf classmate's avatar. These interactions are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Interactions between the hearing participant and the deaf avatar during the VR experience.

Hearing Participant	Essie (Deaf Avatar)
1. Can you read my lips?	Yes.
2. Hi!	Hi! How are you?
3. Is this seat available?	Yes, please, take it.
4. What's your name?	My name is Essie.
5. Do you have a name sign?, What's your name sign?	My sign is (ISENSE sign).
6. Do you live here?	Yes.
7. I'm glad to meet you.	Me too.
8. Is it your first year?	Yes.
9. You like Information Technology (IT), don't you?	More or less.
10. Have you already met any other stu- dents?	No.
11. Don't worry. I can introduce you to many other friends.	That's great.
12. Here comes the teacher. The lesson is about to start.	All right, then.

The SONAR application supports six languages: English, Spanish, Italian, German, Austrian, and Polish. Communication is facilitated through two modes: animated avatars that display International Sign Language (for English) or the corresponding national sign languages for the other languages, and prerecorded videos featuring different signed statements. These videos were recorded by professional sign language interpreters in the respective sign languages of each country.

3.2. Training and Validation Phases

As previously described, the experience is structured into two distinct phases: a Training phase, designed to support sign language learning, and a Validation phase, intended to assess the user’s acquired signing skills.

When the Training phase is selected, the conversation takes place directly, guiding the user through the signing of several basic phrases. During this phase, the user is allowed to practice the signs associated with each phrase while observing the natural flow of the dialog. All signed expressions performed by both the sender (hearing participant) and the receiver (deaf avatar) can be replayed multiple times. In this way, learners can repeatedly observe the movements from within a first-person situated interaction with Essie rather than through a flat video.

In the Validation phase, the same conversational sequence used in Training is presented again. However, whenever the user is required to act as the sender, they must choose one out of three possible signing options displayed in the interface. Each option is presented as a short video embedded in the virtual classroom, and the user selects their answer directly in the 3D scene (by pointing the controller or using a simple confirm gesture), maintaining the feeling of interacting with Essie in a shared space rather than clicking on a 2D menu. A scoring mechanism is employed for assessment: a correct selection on the first attempt yields 50 points, 25 points are awarded if the correct option is selected on the second attempt, and 0 points are assigned if both attempts are incorrect.

Methodologically, the Training phase focuses on information encoding through self-regulated interaction, allowing learners to control the pace and focus of their learning. Conversely, the Validation phase is designed for information retrieval and assessment, as it tests the learner’s ability to recognize and reproduce the signs in a contextualized 3D environment.

Figure 1 illustrates the flow diagram of the proposed experience, detailing the sequence of interactions and decision points that structure the learner’s progression. The diagram summarizes the main stages of the experience, from initial classroom navigation and interaction with the deaf avatar to the selection between Training and Validation modes. It also highlights the different interaction dynamics, feedback mechanisms, and finish conditions that control each phase, providing an overview of the system logic underlying the sign language learning and assessment process.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the SONAR experience.

3.3. Deployment Setup and Interaction with the Environment

Users can interact with the virtual environment through Meta Quest devices, supporting six degrees of freedom (6DoF) tracking. Locomotion can be performed using the standard handheld controllers, enabling both linear displacement and teleportation-based navigation within the virtual classroom.

To facilitate continuous sign language practice and reduce the need for physical controllers during interaction, a controller-free locomotion mechanism based on hand gestures has also been implemented. In this mode, users can navigate the environment by extending both arms. Additional interactions, such as selection or confirmation, are performed through intuitive hand gestures, including pointing with the index finger and confirming selections by closing the fist. This implementation allows for a complete interaction without interrupting signing activities and preserves the benefits of embodied, spatially situated observation that differentiate the VR experience from conventional 2D video-based materials. The immersive 6DoF setup in SONAR enables learners to slightly change their viewpoint relative to Essie, thereby inspecting handshapes, orientations, and trajectories from different angles while remaining within a coherent 3D classroom scene. The choice to use a VR environment instead of a 2D video interface is consistent with prior work showing that immersive VR via HMDs can outperform less immersive methods in terms of learning outcomes and engagement [4,11]

4. Research Questions and Concept of Engagement

This section clarifies the conceptual framework used to interpret engagement in the SONAR environment and states the study's aims. In Section 4.1, we defined the concept of engagement applied to our VR learning scenario, and we introduced the behavioral indicators used to operationalize it: VA, VRF, and PPVT. In Section 4.2, we present the Research Questions that guide the analysis.

4.1. Engagement in the SONAR Environment

As discussed in Section 2.3, engagement in educational settings is commonly conceptualized as comprising cognitive, behavioral, and affective dimensions [30,31]. In VR learning environments, cognitive engagement is associated with learners' attention and mental effort toward mastering the instructional content; behavioral engagement reflects observable participation and interaction within the environment, and affective engagement encompasses motivation, interest, and emotional involvement. In line with recent work on immersive learning and learning analytics, the present study concentrates on behavioral manifestations of engagement that can be captured in a non-invasive way through the interaction between the learner and the VR platform [33,34].

In the context of our SONAR application, three aspects of learner behavior are particularly informative for understanding engagement with the material. The first aspect is how consistently learners direct their attention toward the signing model during instruction [5,6]. The second aspect is the extent to which learners actively decide to revisit the instructional material [8,9]. The third aspect is how long they continue to attend to the visual representation of the signs after playback has finished [35,37]. For this reason, in order to predict user engagement, we choose three behavioral variables: VA, VRF, and PPVT.

VA is defined as the proportion of time in which the user is oriented toward the video screen displaying the signing avatar during both Training and Validation Phases. This definition is grounded in recent research, which has established that gaze-based indicators are valid proxies for attention and cognitive engagement in VR and immersive video learning environments [5,6]. Research has shown that fixation duration on task-relevant regions predicts both engagement and learning outcomes [37]. In sign language learning,

sustained visual focus on the signer is essential to perceive manual articulation, facial expressions, and body movements that jointly convey linguistic information. Studies on embodied learning and sign language teaching with virtual avatars emphasize that learners must maintain stable attention on the signing space to accurately encode handshape, movement, and location [38,47]. This makes VA a natural behavioral correlate of task-relevant attention in sign language contexts.

Operationally, we defined a rectangular Region of Interest (ROI) positioned in the center of the screen, subtending 10° of the visual field, corresponding to the central attention zone. For each frame, we computed the percentage of the target video screen visible within this ROI. We chose head pose over direct eye-tracking because the used VR devices do not provide integrated eye-tracking capabilities. This design choice ensures that the behavioral metrics can be extracted from widely accessible consumer VR hardware, enhancing the scalability and reproducibility of engagement analytics in educational VR applications. Furthermore, this choice is supported by other works demonstrating that head pose effectively identifies attended regions in VR environments [48].

VRF denotes the number of times each training video is reloaded by a learner during the Training phase, normalized by the total time spent in the Training phase. This normalization accounts for individual differences in session duration. This indicator is motivated by research on self-regulated learning and behavioral engagement, which shows that voluntary decisions to revisit instructional content often reflect metacognitive strategies aimed at clarifying misunderstandings, reinforcing memory traces, or preparing for subsequent assessment [8]. Video analytics research has identified that self-regulated learning in video-based contexts involves strategic use of playback controls, including rewinding and replay [8,9,39]. Research on learner clusters has identified that active engagement patterns, characterized by frequent interaction, predict better learning outcomes [40].

In video-based and online learning contexts, fine-grained analyses of pausing, rewinding, and replay sequences have been used to identify segments that learners find difficult and to characterize deeper engagement with challenging parts of the content [9,40]. Learners employ diverse self-regulated strategies with video playback controls, including pausing for reflection, and selective replaying of difficult segments [9]. In the specific case of sign language training, replaying videos allows learners to repeatedly observe complex handshapes, orientations, and movements, which can support the refinement of perceptual discrimination and the formation of robust mental representations of the signs [2]. The strategic, selective nature of replay indicates that learners are engaging in deliberate practice and self-monitoring [8]. For these reasons, VRF is interpreted as an indicator of strategic re-engagement with the instructional material.

PPVT is a metric extracted from the analysis of the Training phase; it captures the duration for which a video remains visible on the screen after its active playback has finished, until the learner either replays it or initiates the next video. Operationally, during this period, the final frame of the video remains frozen and displayed on the virtual screen, while learners retain full freedom of movement within the VR environment; indeed, they can move their heads, move their hands to practice the sign, or shift their body position. The controlled nature of the SONAR classroom environment ensures minimal external distractions during this window; no other animated elements or interactive objects compete for attention. This temporal window is interpreted as an operational proxy for post-presentation processing. During this interval, learners may mentally rehearse the observed signs, inspect articulatory details, or reflect on how the signs relate to previously learned items.

The use of a PPVT as an indirect behavioral indicator is grounded in eye-tracking research showing that dwell time (i.e., the duration of sustained attention on task-relevant

stimuli) is associated with deeper cognitive processing [37]. In multimedia learning environments, longer viewing durations on relevant stimuli have been associated with improved retention of information and deeper cognitive engagement [35]. More specifically, fixation duration research has demonstrated that learners engaged in active cognitive processing show specific patterns of fixation times that differ from passive viewing, and that these patterns predict subsequent learning outcomes [37]. While PPVT does not directly measure internal cognitive states, it serves as a behavioral trace that may reflect the time allocated to such processes.

Embodied learning and motor learning studies further show that extended observation following the demonstration of a movement can facilitate internal simulation and consolidation of motor representations [38,47]. This is especially important for visually mediated skills such as sign language production, where learners must internally simulate and encode complex motor patterns observed in the signing model. The presence of the video on-screen after playback completion provides an opportunity for this post-presentation cognitive processing and motor consolidation. Therefore, PPVT is interpreted as an operational indicator that may index how much additional cognitive and perceptual processing learners devote to each signed phrase once the dynamic motion has ended.

4.2. Research Questions

The analyses in this work focus on the following research questions:

- RQ1: How are behavioral indicators of engagement (namely VA, VRF, and PPVT) related to learning performance in an immersive sign language training scenario?
- RQ2: How do learners' attention and engagement evolve while viewing the sign language videos, and what general temporal patterns emerge in these indicators?

These research questions aim to clarify both the association between behavioral engagement metrics and learning performance, and the temporal dynamics of engagement while learners interact with sign language videos in VR. Our first research question (RQ1) adopts an outcome-oriented perspective, examining whether automatically-derived behavioral indicators predict learning success. Prior research has shown that aggregate engagement measures computed across sessions correlate with learning outcomes in diverse educational contexts [33–35], but none of them are related to sign language environment.

Our second research question (RQ2) adopts a process-oriented perspective, examining how learners' engagement changes over time during the interaction. Since analysis of behavioral traces reveals typical engagement trajectories and temporal patterns in how learners interact with learning content [6,49], by aggregating temporal profiles of visual attention across learners, it is possible to identify general engagement patterns and reveal when engagement peaks or declines during learning activities [6,50].

Together, these two research questions integrate outcome-oriented and process-oriented perspectives, providing complementary insights into how engagement operates in VR-based sign language learning.

5. Experimental Setting

The study involved 117 university students who attended a VR sign language training session lasting approximately 15–20 min, followed by a validation phase of approximately 10–15 min. Each participant was exposed to the same set of interactions (videos; see Table 1), which were always presented in a fixed order. The sample comprised participants with varying levels of prior VR exposure: 56.1% had no previous experience with VR environments, while the remaining 43.9% reported few prior VR interactions. Regarding sign language knowledge, 86% of participants had no prior experience with sign language.

As described in Section 3.3, the application provides two different types of interaction: handled and controller-free. In the present study, all participants used the controller-free hand-tracking modality exclusively. This methodological choice was made to maximize immersion for the sign language learning environment, where continuous hand availability is essential for learners to practice signs while observing instructional videos. The controller-free modality also eliminates potential confounds from controller manipulation during behavioral data collection, ensuring that head orientation tracking for Visual Attention measurement and interaction timestamps for PPVT and VRF calculation reflect genuine learning behaviors rather than device-handling actions.

Each student completed two consecutive phases. In the Training phase, participants freely watched the 12 videos one by one, with the possibility to replay each video (once it had finished) as many times as desired. In the subsequent Validation phase, they answered a quiz in which each item required selecting the video that matched a target signed phrase previously seen in the Training phase. Each quiz item in the Validation phase was associated with exactly one video from the Training phase, as described in Section 3. A Training–Validation session comprising 12 items was implemented because this number allowed the complete protocol to be conducted within approximately 30 min, while maintaining an adequate number of observations per participant. Increasing the number of items would have extended the session duration and potentially introduced fatigue effects that could have confounded the performance measures.

User interaction information were collected throughout the Training and Validation phases. Specifically, VA is calculated in both Training and Validation phases, while VRF and PPVT are only related to the Training Phase. For RQ1, we first examined the distribution of quiz scores and then computed Pearson correlations between the three behavioral engagement variables (i.e., VA, VRF, PPVT) and the performance variable defined as the number of correct answers obtained in the Validation quiz (Section 6.1.1). We then complemented this analysis with a regression study in which the proportion of correct answers was modeled as a function of VA, PPVT, and VRF in order to assess their joint and unique contributions to learning performance (Section 6.1.2). In relation to RQ2, the same time-stamped interaction logs were used to characterise the general evolution of learners' attention and engagement during video viewing, by analysing the temporal patterns of VA, across the Training and Validation phase and within individual videos (Section 6.2).

It is important to note that this study employs a purely correlational design without control conditions. All sessions were conducted under standardized conditions in controlled laboratory settings, using the Meta Quest default parameters; instructions and task structures were kept constant across participants, ensuring consistent exposure to the training materials and interaction procedures. This design allows us to identify predictive relationships but does not permit causal inferences regarding the effects of engagement on learning performance. Experimental validation through controlled designs would be necessary to establish causality.

6. Results

In this section we show all the results associated to RQ1 and RQ2. Specifically, in Section 6.1, we investigate which of the three behavioral indicators is the most informative for predicting the users' learning performance. In Section 6.2, we discuss the dynamic of VA during the Training and Validation phases, highlighting the peaks and the trend of the curve.

6.1. RQ1: How Are Behavioral Indicators of Engagement Related to Learning Performance in an Immersive Sign Language Scenario?

This subsection presents quantitative analyses of user interaction data recorded during the VR sign language session, focusing on the association between engagement metrics and overall performance. In Section 6.1.1 we perform a correlation analysis between behavioral indicators and performance, while in Section 6.1.2 we use a binomial GLM to predict the number of correct answers using the three behavioral indicators as features.

6.1.1. Correlation Between Engagement and Performance

In Figure 2 we show the distribution of correct answers in the Validation phase. The distribution is shifted toward higher scores, with a mean of $\mu = 9.846$ and standard deviation of $\sigma = 2.172$. This indicates that most participants successfully answered the majority of quiz items.

Figure 2. Distribution of correct answers in the Validation phase.

To investigate the relationship between behavioral engagement and learning outcomes, we computed Pearson correlation coefficients between the three engagement metrics defined in Section 4 and quiz performance.

PPVT exhibited a strong positive correlation with performance ($r = 0.66, p < 0.001$), as illustrated in Figure 3a. Participants who maintained videos visible on the screen for extended durations after playback ended, ostensibly engaging in reflection or mental rehearsal, achieved notably better learning outcomes.

Figure 3. Relationships between quiz performance and the three behavioral engagement metrics: (a) Post-Playback Viewing Time (PPVT); (b) Visual Attention (VA); (c) Video Replay Frequency (VRF).

VA showed the strongest correlation with quiz performance ($r = 0.76, p < 0.001$), as shown in Figure 3b. This metric, operationalized as the proportion of time the user’s gaze was oriented toward the video screen, reflects sustained attention directed toward instructional content. The strong positive relationship indicates that participants who

maintained consistent visual focus on the signing model achieved substantially higher quiz scores.

In contrast, VRF displayed a negligible and non-significant correlation with performance ($r = 0.02$, $p = 0.811$), as shown in Figure 3c. This finding indicates that the raw number of times participants replayed videos does not meaningfully predict learning success. The lack of correlation suggests that engagement quality matters substantially more than the sheer quantity of repetitions.

6.1.2. Regression Analysis of Behavioral Engagement and Performance

To examine the joint contribution of behavioral engagement metrics to learning performance, we modeled quiz performance as a function of the three engagement indicators. At the participant level, performance was expressed as the proportion of correct answers in the Validation phase. We fitted a binomial GLM with logit link function, using standardized versions of Visual Attention (VA_z), Post-Playback Viewing Time ($PPVT_z$), and Video Replay Frequency (VRF_z) as predictors :

$$\text{logit}(\text{prop_correct}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 VA_z + \beta_2 PPVT_z + \beta_3 VRF_z \quad (1)$$

Table 2 presents the estimated coefficients on the log-odds scale, their standard errors, z-statistics, significance levels, and corresponding Odds Ratios. VA_z and $PPVT_z$ emerge as positive and highly significant predictors of performance. VRF_z shows a near-zero and non-significant coefficient, indicating negligible additional predictive value once the other metrics are included. The model achieves a Cox-Snell pseudo- R^2 of 0.8309, indicating that these engagement metrics jointly explain a substantial proportion of variance in learning outcomes. It is worth noting that this substantial predictive power is partly attributable to the specific distribution of the performance data (Figure 2). Since the majority of participants achieved high scores (mean = 9.846), the dataset presents a ‘ceiling effect’ where instances of low performance are distinct exceptions. The GLM effectively leverages the engagement metrics (VA_z and $PPVT_z$) to discriminate these specific cases of lower performance from the high-performing majority, resulting in high model fit indices typical of datasets with this type of skewness. For this reason, the pseudo- R^2 value should not be interpreted as evidence of near-complete explanatory power in a general learning context, but rather as an indication that, within this restricted and skewed performance range, the selected behavioral indicators separate high- and low-performing learners relatively well.

Table 2. Binomial GLM for the proportion of correct answers. Predictors are standardized (z-scores). Coefficients are on the log-odds scale with Standard Errors (SE), z-statistics, p-values, and Odds Ratios (OR).

Predictor	Coefficient	SE	z	p-Value	OR
Intercept	1.8194	0.086	21.104	<0.001	—
VA_z	0.7558	0.094	8.040	<0.001	2.129
$PPVT_z$	0.4359	0.088	4.931	<0.001	1.546
VRF_z	−0.0339	0.076	−0.448	0.654	0.967

The positive coefficients for VA_z and $PPVT_z$ indicate that, holding other variables constant, participants exhibiting higher VA and longer PPVT achieve better quiz performance. Since the predictors are standardized, a one-unit increase corresponds to a one standard deviation increase in the respective engagement metric. Interpreted as Odds Ratios, a one standard deviation increase in VA_z multiplies the odds of correctly answering a quiz item by approximately 2.13, while a one standard deviation increase in $PPVT_z$ multiplies the

odds by approximately 1.54. These effect sizes demonstrate that both sustained visual focus on the signing model and additional processing time after playback are strongly associated with successful recognition and comprehension of signed phrases.

Conversely, the coefficient for VRF_z is near zero and not statistically significant ($p = 0.654$). Its Odds Ratio is approximately 0.97, representing essentially no change. This result indicates that, once VA and PPVT are accounted for, the VRF provides no meaningful additional predictive information. The qualitative aspects of engagement appear far more informative for predicting learning outcomes than the quantity of repetitions alone.

Figure 4 displays the GLM predictions for the proportion of correct answers as a function of each standardized engagement metric. In all three panels, blue dots represent observed participant quiz scores, while the red curve shows the model-predicted probability of a correct response when varying one predictor while holding the others at their mean values.

Across the plots, $PPVT_z$ and VA_z show clearly increasing regression curves, visually confirming that longer PPVT and higher VA are associated with higher predicted performance. The nearly flat curve for VRF_z confirms that changes in VRF have a negligible impact on predicted performance, consistent with its non-significant coefficient in Table 2.

Figure 4. Predicted proportion of correct answers from the binomial GLM as a function of each standardized engagement metric. The red curve shows the model-predicted probability of a correct response when varying one predictor while holding the others at their mean values: (a) Post-Playback Viewing Time ($PPVT_z$). Effect of $PPVT_z$ on predicted quiz performance; (b) Visual Attention (VA_z). Effect of VA_z on predicted quiz performance; (c) Video Replay Frequency (VRF_z). Effect of VRF_z on predicted quiz performance.

6.2. RQ2: What Do These Behavioral Metrics Suggest About Learners' Engagement Processes?

Given the findings from RQ1, we focus exclusively on VA as the primary indicator for characterizing engagement processes throughout the training activity. This choice is justified by both empirical and theoretical considerations. In RQ1, VRF showed negligible correlation with learning performance and contributed no significant predictive value in the regression model. PPVT, while correlated with performance, represents a static summary measure aggregated across the entire training session and lacks temporal resolution. In contrast, VA can be measured and sampled at fine temporal scales, providing moment-to-moment information about how learners allocate their visual focus during both Training and Validation activities.

The decision to use VA as a time-varying indicator of engagement aligns with established research on gaze-based measures in learning environments. Eye-tracking research has consistently demonstrated that gaze direction and fixation patterns serve as direct, real-time indicators of where learners direct their attention and, by extension, where they focus their cognitive resources [5,6]. In immersive learning environments, these gaze-based metrics have been operationalized as temporal indicators of engagement precisely because they can be sampled continuously throughout the learning process, allowing researchers to

characterize how engagement unfolds and changes across time [6]. Advanced analytical frameworks have developed temporal profiles of VA, aggregating moment-by-moment gaze data across learners to derive general engagement patterns that reveal when engagement peaks or declines during learning activities [5].

Consequently, in our analysis of RQ2, we use VA as the primary temporal indicator of engagement. Rather than treating engagement as a single static aggregate, we analyze how VA evolves across the sequence of Training and Validation videos, identifying temporal patterns and dynamics that characterize learners' engagement processes during sign language VR training. This process-oriented perspective complements the outcome-oriented analysis from RQ1, revealing not only whether engagement predicts performance, but also how engagement unfolds dynamically as learners interact with the instructional material.

Figure 5 presents the aggregated temporal profile of VA across all 117 participants throughout their complete interaction with the VR application. The profile reveals distinct patterns of engagement that correspond to the different phases and cognitive demands of the learning experience.

Figure 5. Temporal profile of aggregated VA across all participants. The blue curve represents mean VA normalized across video frame progression, with the light blue band indicating the 95% confidence interval. Red stars mark the 24 highest peaks, corresponding to moments of particularly intense visual focus during video playback.

During the initial portion of the profile (0 to approximately 15 percent), VA increases gradually as learners begin their interaction with the application. This slow ramp-up reflects a characteristic pattern in immersive learning environments where participants require time to acclimate to the virtual environment and transition their attentional resources from environmental exploration to focused engagement with instructional content. Research on immersive learning has documented that learners initially allocate attention to environmental exploration and familiarization with interface elements before settling into focused engagement with the learning material [50].

Following this initial phase, the profile shows 12 distinct peaks, each corresponding to one of the 12 training videos presented during the instructional phase. These peaks represent moments of heightened VA during the presentation of signing demonstrations, indicating that learners direct concentrated visual focus toward specific moments within each video. The emergence of distinct peaks suggests that different moments within each training video elicit varying levels of visual attention. In multimedia learning, learners modulate their attentional allocation based on perceived salience and task relevance of different content segments [5,37]. In sign language learning, these peaks likely correspond

to moments when manual articulation, handshape transitions, or facial expressions are most prominent or when linguistic information is densest.

Between consecutive peaks, VA shows noticeable declines before recovering toward the next peak. This oscillating pattern within the training phase reflects characteristic attention dynamics in which learners maintain high focus during moments of high informational density, then experience transient reductions in visual attention in the intervals following these moments. One interpretation is that after observing key articulatory or linguistic information, learners engage in internal processing, reflection, or mental rehearsal rather than maintaining continuous visual focus on the signing model. This pattern is consistent with cognitive science research on attention and working memory, which demonstrates that learners benefit from periods of distributed attention that allow for encoding and consolidation of perceived information [37]. The declines may also reflect natural variations in motor behavior and saliency across the content, where moments of lower visual prominence naturally redirect learner attention.

A marked transition occurs at approximately 55 to 63 percent of the profile, where VA drops to a lower, more stable baseline. This plateau corresponds to the transition from the training phase to the Validation phase. Following the plateau, the profile exhibits a second set of 12 peaks, each corresponding to one of the 12 quiz items in the Validation phase. These peaks appear as learners are presented with recognition and decision-making tasks, indicating moments when quiz items capture their visual attention. The appearance of these validation peaks indicates that learners return to the task with increased visual focus during assessment activities.. These validation peaks indicate sustained engaged visual processing during the recognition and selection tasks required by the quiz.

Immediately following the completion of the validation phase (near 100 percent of the profile), VA shows a sharp, dramatic collapse. This precipitous decline reflects the moment at which learners exit the interactive application and conclude their engagement with the system. The sharp drop indicates that the elevated VA observed throughout both phases is task-driven and stimulus-dependent, contingent on the presence of active instructional or assessment activities.

The temporal structure of VA revealed in this aggregated profile illuminates how learners allocate visual attention across different types of cognitive engagement in sign language learning. The distinct peaks corresponding to training videos reflect intensive visual perception when learners extract motor and linguistic information from signing demonstrations. The presence of peaks during validation, suggests that learners maintain engaged visual processing when retrieving and recognizing previously observed signs. The intervening periods of lower VA may represent cognitive processing windows during which learners consolidate perceived information or mentally rehearse observed signs.

7. Discussion

This study provides empirical evidence regarding the role of behavioral engagement indicators in predicting learning performance in VR-based sign language training, addressing a significant gap in the literature. From the analysis of the users' interaction, we extracted insights about the three behavioral indicators. From a correlational perspective, VA emerges as the most correlated variable with respect to validation quiz performance ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.001$), a result aligned with established literature on eye-tracking and cognitive load theory [37]. Indeed, in the context of sign language, maintaining stable visual attention on the model is essential for accurately perceiving manual articulation, facial expressions, and body movements that jointly convey linguistic information [5,6]. Our results extend these established theoretical principles to the specific domain of VR-based sign language education, a context previously lacking empirical investigation.

PPVT emerges as the second most correlated variable ($r = 0.66, p < 0.001$), suggesting that the time spent observing the video after playback completion may serve as an operational proxy for post-presentation cognitive processes critical for consolidating motor representations [47]. During this temporal window, learners likely engage in internal simulation, perceptual review of observed signs, and reflection on how learned elements relate to prior knowledge. This result is consistent with hypotheses derived from motor learning research, which has demonstrated that extended observation of movement demonstrations, particularly after the movement concludes, facilitates internal simulation and consolidation of motor representations [38]. However, our study did not directly measure internal simulation processes; the observed correlation between PPVT and performance suggests a relationship that may involve such mechanisms, but alternative explanations (e.g., simple memory rehearsal, comparative analysis between signs, or individual differences in processing speed) cannot be excluded based on our data alone. In terms of cognitive load theory, post-playback time may represent a window in which learners deliberately reduce extraneous cognitive load (visual distraction from motion) while maintaining germane cognitive processing (internal review of learned material), although the specific cognitive mechanisms underlying this behavioral pattern warrant further investigation through complementary methods such as concurrent verbalization or neuroimaging.

Notably, VRF ($r = 0.02, p = 0.811$) shows negligible and non-significant correlation with performance, in contrast with some of the related literature [9]. In reality, this reflects a fundamental principle of motor learning research: the quality of deliberate practice outweighs the amount of exposure [37]. This result is conceptually interesting and invites reconsideration of simple models of self-regulated learning that equate replay frequency with engagement level or metacognitive sophistication. In the context of visually mediated motor acquisition tasks such as sign language, attentional quality during initial viewing appears to outweigh the quantity of subsequent repetitions. An alternative interpretation is that replay may sometimes represent a compensatory strategy employed by learners who failed to maintain focused visual attention during initial viewing; in this case, low replay would indicate effective initial perception rather than inferior engagement. This hypothesis merits empirical investigation in future studies employing experimental designs that deliberately manipulate replay opportunities.

The binomial GLM indicates that both standardized VA and PPVT are significant predictors of quiz performance (regression coefficients, odds ratios). Increases in VA are associated with a higher likelihood of correct responses (odds ratio), while PPVT also shows a positive, though more moderate, contribution (odds ratio). In contrast, VRF does not exhibit a meaningful effect on performance (p -value, odds ratio), suggesting a negligible association with quiz outcomes. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power (Cox-Snell pseudo- R^2), which can be partially attributed to the distribution of the performance data: most participants achieved very high scores, resulting in a ceiling effect in which lower performance levels occur only infrequently.

The analysis of the distribution of the VA over time revealed distinct peaks corresponding to training videos and additional peaks during validation, interspersed with periods of reduced attention. This temporal dynamic provides empirical evidence that engagement is not a static global state but rather a dynamic process evolving in response to specific task demands and environmental stimuli [5]. The observed attention dips between peaks may operationally index post-presentation cognitive processing windows during which learners consolidate perceived information, mentally rehearse observed sign sequences, or prepare for the subsequent segment, though alternative explanations such as natural fatigue or task-switching costs cannot be ruled out based on behavioral data alone. This alignment between our empirical observations and established principles of

cognitive science strengthens the validity of our temporal analysis framework and supports interpretation of observed patterns as authentic reflections of learning processes rather than measurement artifacts.

These results validate and extend existing research frameworks on learning analytics and engagement measurement through automatically-derived behavioral indicators extracted from interaction traces [33,34]. They confirm that in the specific educational domain of VR-based sign language learning, automatically-derived behavioral indicators provide reliable and predictively significant signals of learning performance. The null finding for VRF adds an important cautionary note to simplistic self-regulated learning models.

Practically, these results suggest concrete pathways toward attention-aware learning analytics systems in immersive sign language educational applications. VA and PPVT signals could be computed in real time within educational VR applications, enabling adaptive feedback and targeted instructional interventions. However, implementation of such adaptive systems requires rigorous experimental validation before large-scale deployment, as overly intrusive feedback could produce counterintuitive effects.

Despite these interesting implications, the study presents some limitations. The sample comprises 117 European university students without significant prior sign language experience; results may differ substantially in more diverse populations including children, older adults, individuals with cognitive disabilities, or those with prior sign language knowledge. The learning material was restricted to 12 basic phrases within a coherent narrative context; tasks of greater scope, higher grammatical complexity, larger sign sets, or decontextualized content could alter engagement dynamics or learning performance substantially. Additionally, while our behavioral indicators serve as operational proxies for underlying cognitive processes, they do not provide direct access to learners' internal mental states. Future work incorporating complementary measures such as think-aloud protocols or physiological indicators could triangulate these findings and provide richer insights into the cognitive mechanisms underlying the observed behavioral patterns.

Moreover this work is a correlational study, indeed, while our regression model demonstrates robust covariation between VA, PPVT, and performance, we cannot determine whether high VA or extended PPVT directly cause improved learning outcomes, or whether both are consequences of other learner characteristics such as motivation or prior VR knowledge. Future experimental studies that systematically manipulate engagement indicators would be necessary to establish causal relationships and test whether interventions targeting these behavioral indicators can effectively enhance learning outcomes.

Finally, the study focuses solely on immediate learning within a single session; it is still unclear whether the engagement effects observed persist over longer periods, or how well brief engagement patterns predict performance in longer-term learning protocols.

8. Conclusions and Future Works

This paper shows that objective behavioral traces collected in a VR sign language learning application can predict learning outcomes and reveal time-varying engagement dynamics, with VA and PPVT emerging as the most informative indicators and VRF providing limited predictive value in this setting. In addition, aggregated VA profiles highlight structured engagement patterns across training and validation, reinforcing the value of temporal process analysis alongside outcome prediction.

These findings support a practical path toward attention-aware learning analytics in immersive sign language education, where engagement signals can be used not only for post-hoc evaluation but also for designing adaptive support. A promising direction is to move from prediction to causally grounded design by validating whether real-time,

attention-contingent feedback and targeted review policies measurably improve learning efficiency and retention.

In the future, we plan to extend our dataset; indeed, the participants were university students who generally performed well. Future studies involving more heterogeneous populations or more challenging tasks might yield more moderate goodness-of-fit values as the variance in performance increases. Other future work should incorporate richer temporal and sequence-based modeling of interactions (beyond counts) and assess generalization across different languages, sign sets, and longer-term learning protocols.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
DHH	Deaf and Hard-of-Hearing
ER	Extended Reality
GLM	Generalized Linear Model
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
ISENSE	Innovative Supporting sErVICES for uNiversity Students with dEafness
PPVT	Post-Playback Viewing Time
RQ1	Research Question 1
RQ2	Research Question 2
VA	Visual Attention
VR	Virtual Reality
VRF	Video Replay Frequency

References

1. Yu, Z.; Xu, W. A meta-analysis and systematic review of the effect of virtual reality technology on users' learning outcomes. *Comput. Appl. Eng. Educ.* **2022**, *30*, 1470–1484.
2. Wang, J.; Ivrrissimtzis, I.; Li, Z.; Shi, L. The Impact of 2D and 3D Gamified VR on Learning American Sign Language. *arXiv* **2024**, arXiv:2405.08908.
3. Berrezueta-Guzman, S.; Daya, R.; Wagner, S. Virtual reality in sign language education: Opportunities, challenges, and the road ahead. *Front. Virtual Real.* **2025**, *6*, 1625910.
4. Mallek, F.; Mazhar, T.; Shah, S.F.A.; Ghadi, Y.Y.; Hamam, H. A review on cultivating effective learning: Synthesizing educational theories and virtual reality for enhanced educational experiences. *PeerJ Comput. Sci.* **2024**, *10*, e2000.
5. Abeysinghe, Y.; Hasan, S.; Tanveer, M. Assessing Visual Attention in Gaze-Based VR Learning Environments Using Eye-Tracking Measures. In Proceedings of the GSGA Research Conference, Norfolk, VA, USA, 11 April 2025.
6. Adhanom, I.B.; MacNeilage, P.; Folmer, E. Eye tracking in virtual reality: A broad review of applications and challenges. *Virtual Real.* **2023**, *27*, 1481–1505.
7. Ekin, M.; Krejtz, K.; Duarte, C.; Duchowski, A.T.; Krejtz, I. Prediction of intrinsic and extraneous cognitive load with oculometric and biometric indicators. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 5213. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-89336-y>.
8. Wang, J.Y.; Yang, C.H.; Liao, W.C.; Yang, K.C.; Chang, I.W.; Sheu, B.C.; Ni, Y.H. Highly engaged video-watching pattern in asynchronous online pharmacology course in pre-clinical 4th-Year medical students was associated with a good self-expectation, understanding, and performance. *Front. Med.* **2022**, *8*, 799412.
9. Galbraith, J. Active viewing: And oxymoron in video-based instruction. In Proceedings of the Society for Applied Learning Technologies Conference, Kissimmee, FL, USA, 18–20 February 2004.
10. Tao, L.; Cukurova, M.; Song, Y. Learning analytics in immersive virtual learning environments: A systematic literature review. *Smart Learn. Environ.* **2025**, *12*, 43.
11. Hamilton, D.; McKechnie, J.; Edgerton, E.; Wilson, C. Immersive virtual reality as a pedagogical tool in education: A systematic literature review of quantitative learning outcomes and experimental design. *J. Comput. Educ.* **2021**, *8*, 1–32.
12. Chen, B.; Wang, Y.; Wang, L. The effects of virtual reality-assisted language learning: A meta-analysis. *Sustainability* **2022**, *14*, 3147.
13. Huang, X.; Zou, D.; Cheng, G.; Xie, H. A systematic review of AR and VR enhanced language learning. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 4639.
14. Harris, C.; Sun, B. Assessing the effect of interactivity design in VR based second language learning tool. In *Proceedings of the 2022 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2022; pp. 18–25.
15. Yigitbas, E.; Schmidt, M.; Bucchiarone, A.; Bassanelli, S.; Engels, G. Gamification-and virtual reality-based learning environment for UML class diagram modeling. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2024; pp. 1–10.
16. Upadhyay, B.; Chalil Madathil, K.; Hegde, S.; Anderson, D.; Wooldridge, E.; Presley, D.; Perez, L.; Reid, B. Barriers toward the implementation of extended reality (XR) technologies to support education and training in workforce development programs. In *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*; SAGE Publications Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA, USA, 2024; Volume 68, pp. 265–269.
17. Liu, J.Y.W.; Yin, Y.H.; Kor, P.P.K.; Cheung, D.S.K.; Zhao, I.Y.; Wang, S.; Su, J.J.; Christensen, M.; Tyrovolas, S.; Leung, A.Y. The effects of immersive virtual reality applications on enhancing the learning outcomes of undergraduate health care students: Systematic review with meta-synthesis. *J. Med. Internet Res.* **2023**, *25*, e39989.
18. Odunga, J.O.; Musuva, P.M.; Ndiege, J.R.A. Exploring Emerging Technologies for Inclusive Education in Students with Learning Disabilities: A Systematic Literature Review. In *Proceedings of the 2025 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2025; pp. 1–13.
19. Chalkiadakis, A.; Seremetaki, A.; Kanellou, A.; Kallishi, M.; Morfopoulou, A.; Moraitaki, M.; Mastrokoulou, S. Impact of artificial intelligence and virtual reality on educational inclusion: A systematic review of technologies supporting students with disabilities. *Educ. Sci.* **2024**, *14*, 1223.
20. Moreno-Cruz, A.; Muñoz-Arteaga, J.; Ponce-Gallegos, J.C.; Cardona-Reyes, H.; Collazos-Ordóñez, C. Reinforcing Inclusive Education with Virtual Reality: Strengthening Knowledge with the STEAM Approach for Students with Disabilities. *CLEI Electron. J.* **2025**, *28*(4), 1–19.
21. Franze, A.; Loetscher, T.; Gallomario, N.C.; Szapak, A.; Lee, G.; Michalski, S. Immersive virtual reality is more effective than non-immersive devices for developing real-world skills in people with intellectual disability. *J. Intellect. Disabil. Res.* **2024**, *68*, 1358–1373.
22. Creed, C.; Al-Kalbani, M.; Theil, A.; Sarcar, S.; Williams, I. Inclusive AR/VR: Accessibility barriers for immersive technologies. *Univers. Access Inf. Soc.* **2024**, *23*, 59–73.

23. Moreno-Cruz, A.; Muñoz-Arteaga, J.; Ponce-Gallegos, J.C.; Gutiérrez-Vela, F.L. Agile Production of Inclusive Learning Environments with Virtual Reality to Support Bachelor Students with Disabilities. In *IEEE Revista Iberoamericana de Tecnologías del Aprendizaje*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2025.
24. González-Afonso, M.C.; Perdomo-López, C.d.l.Á.; Plasencia-Carballo, Z.; Pérez-Jorge, D. Inclusive education beyond formal settings: AR and VR as accessibility strategies for deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals. In *Frontiers in Education*; Frontiers Media SA: Lausanne, Switzerland, 2025; Volume 10, p. 1715885.
25. Ubur, S.D. [DC] Enhancing Accessibility and Emotional Expression in Educational Extended Reality for Deaf and Hard of Hearing: A User-Centric Investigation. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2024; pp. 1136–1137.
26. El Ghouli, O.; Othman, A. Virtual reality for educating Sign Language using signing avatar: The future of creative learning for deaf students. In *Proceedings of the 2022 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2022; pp. 1269–1274.
27. Immanuel, J.; Berrezueta-Guzman, S. Accessible American Sign Language Learning in Virtual Reality via Inverse Kinematics. In *Virtual Worlds*; MDPI: Basel, Switzerland, 2025; Volume 4, p. 57.
28. Wen, H.; Xu, Y.; Li, L.; Ru, X.; Wu, Z.; Fu, Y.; Zheng, X.; Wang, X. Enhancing Sign Language Teaching: A Mixed Reality Approach for Immersive Learning and Multi-Dimensional Feedback. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2024; pp. 740–745.
29. Bisio, A.; Yeguas-Bolívar, E.; Aparicio-Martínez, P.; Redel-Macías, M.D.; Pinzi, S.; Rossi, S.; Taborri, J. Training program on sign language: Social inclusion through Virtual Reality in ISENSE project. In *Proceedings of the 2023 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRINE)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2023; pp. 104–109.
30. Wang, M.T.; Degol, J.S. Staying Engaged: Knowledge and Research Needs in Student Engagement. *Child Dev. Perspect.* **2014**, *8*, 137–143. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12073>.
31. Fredricks, J.A.; McColskey, M.T. The measurement of student engagement: A comparative analysis of various methods and student self-report instruments. In *Handbook of Research on Student Engagement*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2012; pp. 763–782. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-2018-7_37.
32. Lin, X.P.; Li, B.B.; Yao, Z.N.; Yang, Z.; Zhang, M. The impact of virtual reality on student engagement in the classroom: A critical review. *Front. Psychol.* **2024**, *15*:1360574. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1360574>.
33. Ai, D.; Xiao, J.; Xing, L.; Li, T.; Yang, G.; Fang, G. Virtual Reality Technology in Education: Dynamic Analysis of Student Engagement and Cognitive Load. In *Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on Distance Education and Learning (ICDEL)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2025; pp. 298–302.
34. Solé-Beteta, X.; Navarro, J.; Gajšek, B.; Guadagni, A.; Zaballos, A. A data-driven approach to quantify and measure students' engagement in synchronous virtual learning environments. *Sensors* **2022**, *22*, 3294. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22093294>.
35. Winter, M.; Mordel, J.; Mendzheritskaya, J.; Biedermann, D.; Ciordas-Hertel, G.P.; Hahnel, C.; Bengs, D.; Wolter, I.; Goldhammer, F.; Drachsler, H.; et al. Behavioral trace data in an online learning environment as indicators of learning engagement in university students. *Front. Psychol.* **2024**, *15*, 1396881. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1396881>.
36. Bozkir, E.; Özdel, S.; Wang, M.; David-John, B.; Gao, H.; Butler, K.; Jain, E.; Kasneci, E. Eye-tracked Virtual Reality: A Comprehensive Survey on Methods and Privacy Challenges. *arXiv* **2023**, arXiv:2305.14080.
37. Negi, S.; Mitra, R. Fixation duration and the learning process: An eye tracking study with subtitled videos. *J. Eye Mov. Res.* **2020**, *13*(6).
38. Bagher, M.M.; Sajjadi, P.; Wallgrün, J.O.; La Femina, P.C.; Klippel, A. Move the object or move the user: The role of interaction techniques on embodied learning in VR. *Front. Virtual Real.* **2021**, *2*, 695312.
39. Mo, C.Y.; Wang, C.; Dai, J.; Jin, P. Video playback speed influence on learning effect from the perspective of personalized adaptive learning: A study based on cognitive load theory. *Front. Psychol.* **2022**, *13*, 839982.
40. Yoon, M.; Lee, J.; Jo, I.H. Video learning analytics: Investigating behavioral patterns and learner clusters in video-based online learning. *Internet High. Educ.* **2021**, *50*, 100806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2021.100806>.
41. Mirriahi, N.; Vigentini, L. Analytics of learner video use. *Handb. Learn. Anal.* **2017**, *1*, 251–267.
42. Zhang, Y.; Wang, H.; Shi, B.E. User Engagement Correlates Better with Behavioral than Physiological Measures in a Virtual Reality Robotic Rehabilitation System. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2024; pp. 5189–5194.
43. Gorin, H.; Patel, J.; Qiu, Q.; Merians, A.; Adamovich, S.; Fluet, G. A review of the use of gaze and pupil metrics to assess mental workload in gamified and simulated sensorimotor tasks. *Sensors* **2024**, *24*, 1759.
44. Haar, S.; Sundar, G.; Faisal, A.A. Embodied Virtual Reality for the Study of Real-World Motor Learning. *PLoS ONE* **2021**, *16*, e0245717.

45. Harris, D.J.; et al. The Effect of a Virtual Reality Environment on Gaze Behaviour and Motor Skill Learning. *Psychol. Sport Exerc.* **2020**, *50*, 101721.
46. Lehrman, A.L. Embodied Learning Through Immersive Virtual Reality: Theoretical Perspectives for Art and Design Education. *Behav. Sci.* **2025**, *15*, 917.
47. Dastmalchi, M.R.; Goli, A. Embodied learning in virtual reality: Comparing direct and indirect interaction effects on educational outcomes. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2024; pp. 1–7.
48. Higgins, P.; Barron, R.; Matuszek, C. Head pose as a proxy for gaze in virtual reality. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Workshop on Virtual, Augmented, and Mixed Reality for HRI (VAM-HRI)*, online, 7–10 March 2022.
49. Prakash, A.; Rajendran, R. Decoding Learner Behavior in Virtual Reality Education: Insights from Epistemic Network Analysis and Differential Sequence Mining. In *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2025.
50. Shadiev, R.; Li, D. A review study on eye-tracking technology usage in immersive virtual reality learning environments. *Comput. Educ.* **2023**, *196*, 104681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104681>.

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